

Classroom Management: The Challenge of Change

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ABSTRACT

Undesirable behavior is inevitable inside and outside the school premises. This research addresses the importance of classroom management as one of the important factor that prevents the occurrence of undesirable behavior of the learners. Based on the findings, the ideal classroom management practices lead and connect teachers and learners to meet the model desirable behavior inside and outside the school premises. Indicators include: Establishing clear learning outcomes, behavior management and maximizing in giving praise to the learners. Classroom management has shown to be one of the most important factors that teachers need to consider before the school year. The data has shown that in dealing with students behavior, teacher must develop a strategy that not just only address a single behavior but a multi strategy that meet the needs of the learners.

KEYWORDS: Classroom Management, Desirable behavior, Learning Outcomes, Praise

INTRODUCTION

Within the last decade there is massive research about the importance and ideal classroom management. Most have been special education programs initially centered on emotionally disturbed children or children with classroom behavior problems (Hewett, 1964; Patterson, 1965; Zimmerman, 1962).

It is not undeniable that Classroom management is considered one of the most challenging issues in teaching and learning process. Creating an environment that promotes conducive for learning is probably the most important and one of the most difficult tasks a teacher faces (Canning, 2004).

Moreover, student misbehavior is something that every teacher encounters during his or her teaching career. Student misbehavior is detrimental, because it affects the learning of the student misbehaving, the teacher who is instructing, and the other students in the classroom that are trying to learn (Zakaria, et al., 2013) Kulinna stated that "Student misbehaviors can threaten the effectiveness of a class learning environment" (p. 21). Misbehavior, such as daydreaming, may not affect the learning of others, but is still problematic. This type of misbehavior affects the learning of the student misbehaving, because he or she is missing valuable information and may fall behind academically. If a student's behavior is of a threatening nature, the teacher and the students may feel unsafe and the teacher's authority may be challenged. The learning of other students is affected when they are distracted and can't focus on the material being taught. If the misbehavior is not addressed and remedied, other students may join in on the

behavior(s), which will lead to complete chaos and reflect negatively on the teacher's ability to manage the class. Once the misbehavior evolves into multiple participants, the situation is much more difficult to diffuse. Misbehavior affects the teacher who is instructing, because he or she will need to stop teaching in order to handle the misbehavior, which is time consuming. When teaching comes to a halt, the teacher is not able to maintain his or her lesson schedule and may not be able to teach a lesson at all, or the lesson will have to be shortened. Rushing through a lesson can cause the teacher to miss pertinent information and therefore interferes with the teacher's effectiveness (McCaw, 2018).

Moreover, children are society's investment in the future. Schools are provided to teach skills which will enable them to lead rewarding and fruitful lives. The measurement of how well they have learned these skills, their achievement, is of high interest to parents and educators. Presently much emphasis is placed on achievement and those variables which influence achievement. This study is targeted on science achievement and specific factors that influence student success in achieving (McGarity et al. 1984). Further it is indeed that misbehavior in the classroom makes it difficult for students to learn and for teachers to teach.

Classroom Management

Classroom management has been defined in many different ways. Teachers often view classroom management as a list of tricks or suggestions (Landau, 2009). In any classroom regardless of grade-level, the potential for conflict is inevitable. It is the job of the teacher to address and attempt to prevent such conflicts. Wong, Wong, Rogers and Brooks

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(2012) explain that there are three elements which make an effective teacher. In addition to teaching for lesson mastery and practicing positive expectations, classroom management makes an effective teacher. Therefore, a teacher cannot be effective without the ability to deal with potential conflicts. In the absence of classroom management skills, the effectiveness of quality instruction is compromised as well (Brooks, 2012).

According to Shin & Koh (2007) managing student behavior has always been a primary concern of teachers for student misbehaviors have interfered with a positive learning environment. Doyle (1980) also states that maintaining order in a classroom is a basic task of teaching as management activities lead to the establishment and maintenance of those conditions in which instruction can take place effectively and efficiently. There is accumulating evidence from meta-analyses of variables that influence school learning and that classroom management has been identified as one of the variables that has greatest influence on school learning (Freiberg, 1999). Today, classroom management is becoming an increasing problem for teachers and administrators in primary schools because of changes in educational environments.

Short-Term Risks Associated with Poor Classroom Management

Other than negatively influencing student learning, there are many other risks associated with the use of ineffective classroom management methods. In a study conducted by Stichter and colleagues (2006), teachers who used ineffective classroom management strategies experienced consistent student disturbances and an increased number of verbal interruptions. Approximately six percent of students in an average classroom have behavior problems that require intervention. In addition to these students, there are typically many others who exhibit minor inappropriate behaviors that interfere with their own or other students' learning (Farrell, 2005, Little 2003, as cited in Clunies-Ross et al., 2008). According to Hart (2010), these minor disruptions (such as talking out, being out of seat, etc.; Leftlot et al., 2010) occur most often, and their cumulative effects can be especially harmful; retention (Bali, Anagnostopoulos, & Roberts, 2005) and placement in more restrictive educational environments (i.e., special education; Gottlieb, Gottlieb, & Trongone, 1991) are two examples of these cumulative effects.

Long-Term Risks Associated with Poor Classroom Management

According to Reinke and colleagues (2008), the use of ineffective classroom management methods is also related to negative effects on students' academic, behavioral, and social functioning across time. One of these long-term effects is teacher burnout; teachers who lack effective classroom discipline experience more stress and burnout. Hastings and Bham (2003) found that various aspects of student classroom behavior (e.g., disrespect, lack of student sociability, and lack of attentiveness) differentially predicted various aspects of teacher burnout (e.g., emotional exhaustion, depersonalizing students, and lack of feelings of personal accomplishment). Research has consistently shown that teacher stress affects the teacher's performance, physical and emotional well-being as well as that of their families', and the school as a whole (Clunies-Ross et al., 2008). The most common teacher complaints are related to

disruptive behaviors such as inattention, overactivity, and noncompliance (Goldstein, 1995, as cited in Little & Akin-Little, 2008). According to Reinke and colleagues (2008), disruptive classroom behavior is defined as "any statements or actions by an individual student or group of students that disrupt or interfere with ongoing classroom activities.

Moreover, Classroom management is often an area of concern, especially for newer teachers. When classroom management breaks down, learning will suffer. The ability to manage the classroom naturally so that the managing of the classroom is not a focal point and does not take away from the instructional process is essential. Classroom Management is a means to an end, not the end in itself. Teachers, who focus only on managing the classroom, will often have a classroom that is devoid of excitement and energy. Teachers who focus only on instruction will often have a classroom that is interesting, exciting, and engaging, but one where students can easily be distracted from the job at hand and one where the noise can easily interfere with learning. It takes a balance between the management of students and their behavior, and sound engaging instruction for a teacher to be truly effective (London, 2015).

Furthermore, effective classroom management strategies are vital, in order to create and maintain a smooth-running, safe, and productive learning environment. Teaching and learning may take place through effective classroom management. Wang, Haertel, & Walberg (1994) believed that classroom management greatly influence classroom climate and at the same time promote students engagement in classroom activities and quality of learning.

Yavuz (2009) also said that when teachers adopted the role of creating and maintaining an effective learning environment through organized classroom management teaching-learning process will become more successful compared to the teachers who want to have power and emphasize discipline in the class. Bradley, Pauley, and Parley (2005), added that students affective and cognitive development will be improved when positive student-teacher relationship and increase motivation in the classroom is practice. Good classroom managers will create a friendly learning environment and do not use verbal reprimand, threaten, embarrass, suspend or expel students (Geiger, 2000).

Objective of the Study

To sum up the related studies above it can be noticed and embrace the importance of classroom management in the teaching and learning process. However, this issue has not address in some schools in the Philippines. Hence, this research would find out what are the best strategies and practices of classroom management in a global perspective.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The importance of classroom management in the school is not undeniable. Below are the lists of best practices that were examined in order to meet the needs of the teachers and learners in the learning process that create conducive learning environment that promotes quality learning.

Establishing Clear Learning Outcomes

Clear goals and objectives allow students to monitor their own progress all year 'round and correct their efforts as necessary. If students know what they need to accomplish,

they can look at their results as they go and identify barriers to achieving those goals. Further, communicating the learning goals at the beginning of a unit of instruction has found that it could enhance communication between teachers and students.

Figure1. Establishing Clear Learning Outcomes

Based on the data gathered, it can be noticed that establishing clear learning outcomes to the learners is very fundamental in achieving intended learning outcomes. Establishing a set of expected behavior got the highest weighted mean. This implies that teachers must communicate the expected behavior that the learners need to demonstrate inside the classroom. Followed with documenting the rules given. This implied that it is not enough that you just inform the learners; it also suggested that you will document the agreed expected behavior so that the learners are well motivated to perform desirable inside and outside the classroom. Goodwin (2019) stated that Let the students know what the rules and expectations are on the first day of class. It would also be wise to communicate your expectations to their parents. Send home a list of the rules for parents to review, sign off on, and return to you. Further, teachers must model their expectations for the students. Let them see what you expect of them, and provide them with opportunities to practice them.

Behavior Management

Behavior management include all of the actions and conscious inactions to enhance the probability people, individually and in groups, choose behaviors which are personally fulfilling, productive, and socially acceptable. There is a great deal of research related to behavior change and behavior management.

Figure2. Behavior Management

According to the article Healthyplace.com (2019) positive reinforcement is the most powerful and useful method of changing or developing behaviors. Unfortunately, good

behavior is usually ignored in most homes, at school, and at work. Reinforcement is very familiar to everyone, but it is not used as often as it should be. In fact, if you master the use of positive reinforcement with your child, you will notice really dramatic improvements in behavior. The difficulty is in knowing how to use reinforcement and then in actually using it. Based on the data, positive reinforcement has prevailed as significant predictor in handling learner's behavior. Bain (2007) stated that Positive reinforcement is any event that follows a behavior and increases the likelihood that the behavior will be repeated. Positive reinforcement motivates students to do what they are capable of doing. This implies that to maintain motivation and interest of the learners' positive reinforcements must employed in the classroom such as praise and nonverbal communication (smile or thumbs up), or give rewards as token or stickers. Therefore in order for the teachers to maintain the desirable behavior of the learners teachers must utilize ways that learners develop their full potential to be a responsible students not just for their teachers but also to their classmates.

Maximizing the importance of Praise

Researchers have shown that the use of rewards in the classroom, such as praise, can condition students to respond positively to tasks and can encourage students in many positive ways: like helping them pay more attention to detail and giving them more incentive to try harder.

Figure3. Maximizing the importance of Praise

Teacher praise is one tool that can be a powerful motivator for students. According to Burnett (2011) the power of praise in changing student behavior is that it both indicates teacher approval and informs the student about how the praised academic performance or behavior conforms to teacher expectations. Parents and educators agree that praise is critical to developing a child's self-esteem, which can influence scholastic performance (Rhett, 2011). Based on the previous studies and results on the figure about, it cannot be denied that praise is one of the important formula in achieving the desired objects and goals of the school. Based on the data gathered, in giving praise you must be specific on what is the behavior shown by the learners. Followed by giving positive feedback to the learners, this implies that giving positive will likely to encourage them to do more and achieve more. According to the article Future learn (2018) giving positive feedback encourages them to think critically about their work and to reflect on what they need to do to improve it. helps them see their learning in new ways and gain increased satisfaction from it. Hence, giving positive feedback is essential in dealing with learners behavior.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, classroom management has shown to be one of the most important factors that teachers need to consider before the school year. The data has shown that in dealing with students behavior, teacher must develop a strategy that not just only address a single behavior but a multi strategy that meet the needs of the learners.

Recommendation

The researchers agreed that learners vary from each other; hence, teachers should develop a plan to eliminate or prevent the occurrence of undesirable behavior of the learners through assessing learner's behavioral circumstances.

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